

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Senda****FIRST NAME: Mitsuaki****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Prof. Cleenewerck & Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR ACA-401D

QUESTION 1

What is "devil's advocate?" and why should it be done in writing a dissertation?

- a) For improving the quality of your dissertation, to let others detect some lurks with attacking critically (all phases).
- b) To clarify opposite opinions (planning phase).
- c) About a result of data analysis, to make hypothesis deny it and to re-analyze with it. (data analysis phase).
- d) To draw out participant's real opinion with asking questions that make them angry (esearch phase).

Correct answer: (a)¹

QUESTION 2

In analyzing and interpreting findings, which of the following is **not correct** about what you should check?

- a) Have you omitted throughout your discussion for unclear/ambiguous language?
- b) Are the major themes interrelated to show a higher level of analysis and abstraction?

¹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map From Beginning to End*, SAGE Publications, 2008, 174.

- c) If you have chosen to revisit and reflect on your initial assumptions as stated in your opening chapter, do you flesh these out sufficiently in terms of your study's findings?
- d) Have you acknowledged that there are multiple ways of interpreting findings and that you remain open to other interpretive possibilities?

Correct answer: (a)²

QUESTION 3

Which is **not** a feature of the current version of Zotero?

- a) To scan books into Zotero from your iPhone or iPad.
- b) To update data in your library automatically when these sources are changed.
- c) To save streaming lines from webpages.
- d) To reformat your entire document in any of the over 9,000 citation styles easily.

Correct answer: (b)³

QUESTION 4

Which is **not** a feature of Grammarly?

- a) In-depth recommendations based on context.
- b) Write with more clarity by writing confidently.
- c) Detect difference of meaning between English you write and your mother tongue.
- d) Spots passive voice issues.

Correct answer: (c)⁴

QUESTION 5

Which is **not** the reason of citation in writing dissertations?

- a) To give credit.

² Ibid., 151.

³ "Zotero Blog," Roy Rosenzweig Center for History and New Media, last modified November 5, 2018, accessed June 3, 2019, <https://www.zotero.org/blog/category/features/>.

⁴ "Grammarly Review (May 2019): The Best or Overhyped?" Brad Smith, accessed June 3, 2019, <https://grammargang.com/grammarly-review/>.

- b) To assure readers about the scarcity of your facts.
- c) To show readers the research tradition that informs your work.
- d) To help readers follow or extend your research.

Correct answer: (b)⁵

QUESTION 6

According to Turabian, it is difficult to cite online sources. Select one that is not the reason.

- a) Many websites have many identifiable author, publisher, or sponsor. This makes them the equivalent of any other anonymous source, unlikely to be authoritative or reliable enough to use without serious qualification. The same caution applies to content such as user comments that are posted under pseudonyms, even if the website or blog they are posted on is considered a reliable source.
- b) Online content can be revised without notice, and there are no standards for indicating revisions. A revision date on one website may indicate correction of a spelling error while on another it may mark changes in factual data or claims.
- c) Online content may be simultaneously available from more than one site, some more reliable than others.
- d) Most online sources are located through a URL (Uniform Resource Locator), but URLs come and go. You cannot always be certain they will be available months, week, or even days later, and their disappearance would make it difficult or impossible for you or your readers to find the content you originally consulted.

Correct answer: (a)⁶

QUESTION 7

According to The Bitcoin Energy Consumption Index, which equals to the total energy demand to require to mine bitcoin in 2017?

- a) 0.29 million households in the Asia each year.
- b) 2.9 million households in the US each year.
- c) 29 million households in the UK each year.
- d) 290 million households in China each year.

Correct answer: (b)⁷

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., Eighth edition. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 86.

⁶ Ibid., 88.

QUESTION 8

According to the video text “State Specific Paradigm and Philosophical Assumptions Informing Your Study,” which is the ontological stance of social constructivism?

- a) Beliefs and values are socially constructed.
- b) Consideration of participants’ beliefs and values during the construction of realities.
- c) Co-creation of reality between participants and researcher.
- d) Participants and researcher develop multiple realities through interaction.

Correct answer: (d)⁸

QUESTION 9

Hanson (2012) defines it simply as the use of the internet and new information & communications technologies to help carry out diplomatic objectives. He outlines eight policy goals for digital diplomacy. Select the **wrong** one in them.

- a) Public diplomacy: To maintain contact with audiences as they migrate online and to harness new communications tools to listen to and target important audiences with key messages and to influence major online influencers.
- b) Consular communications and response: To create direct, personal communications channels with citizens travelling overseas, with manageable communications in crisis situations.
- c) Internet freedom: Creation of technologies to keep the internet free and open. This has the related objectives of promoting freedom of speech and democracy as well as undermining authoritarian regimes.
- d) Policy planning: To allow for effective oversight, coordination and planning of international policy government, in response to the internationalization of the egalitarianism.

Correct answer: (d)⁹

⁷ Linkov,Igor, Benjamin D.Trimp, Kelsey Poinatte-Jones, and Marie-Valentine Florin. “Governance Strategies for a Sustainable Digital World.” Sustainability 2018, 4, accessed June 10, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323019402_Governance_Strategies_for_a_Sustainable_Digital_World.

⁸ Philip Adu,Ph.D, "Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study," accessed May 22, 2019, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&feature=youtu.be>.

⁹ Olubukola S. Adesina. “Foreign Policy in an Era of Digital Diplomacy.” Cogent Social Sciences 3, no. 1 2017, 3, accessed June 10, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/310796852_Foreign_policy_in_an_era_of_digital_diplomacy.

QUESTION 10

In following components of three abbreviations, which is **not** correct?

- a) ead.= in the same place; author (female form of ibid.)
et seq.= and the following pages
ex officio= out of one's duty or office
- b) sc. = that is to say, namely
supra=above
scil.= that is to say, namely
- c) locus classicus= standard or most authoritative source
loc. cit.= in the place already mentioned; relates to sources before the immediately prior citation
lupus=simultaneously.
- d) v.= see; look up
v.v.= the other way round
viva= oral examination

Correct answer: (c)¹⁰

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ EUCLID, *ACA-401 COURSEPACK PERIOD 1. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions*, 2019.